

Effects of Burnout and Emotional Stress on Social Life in Employees

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-9, 2023, p. 76 – 100. - 0099-0001-2309-0104.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") "EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform." ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

CURRENT SCIENCE

Assoc. prof. Osman Doruk

""• *Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic*" ("CURRENT SCIENCE A Different Look at Traffic Sociology and Driver ...") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• *The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this* ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• *Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days.*"" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Article Publication Date: 09. 2023

**St. Clements University Industrial and
Organizational Psychology**

Article Type: Review

PhD Student /Yeşim SIRAKAYA

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER

Orcid ID: 0009-0004-2558-8194

Orcid ID: 0000-0001-5896-2956

2

**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI)
EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER
KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY
PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS:
ASI@EUROPE.DE**

Head of the Department of
Psychology at St Clements University

Abstract

Burnout and emotional stress have been shown to be correlated with challenges in effectively accomplishing professional duties and effectively handling work-related obligations, including the specific challenge of working remotely. Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, employees who were socially isolated and lacked support were found to be at a higher risk of experiencing professional disconnection and feelings of inadequacy. This disconnection extended to their relationship with the workplace, leading to heightened work-related pressures, employee burnout, and emotional fatigue. These findings have been supported by various studies conducted by Dionisi et al. (2012, 2021), Holmes et al. (2021), Rapp et al. (2021), and Singh et al. (2022). Employees who engaged in remote work had a higher propensity for experiencing diminished levels of positive affect, which in turn may contribute to the emergence of negative affective states, the development of burnout syndrome, and heightened reactivity to occupational stressors. The implementation of mandatory remote work had a

significant influence on employee performance, leading to a decline in productivity, work engagement, and job satisfaction. Consequently, this decline had adverse effects on subjective and psychological well-being. The provision of social support inside the workplace is crucial for enhancing workers' professional dedication and psychological welfare, particularly in the context of remote work facilitated by technology. The decline in cognitive performance can be attributed to various factors, including inconsistent decision-making in human resource management, an unsupportive work environment, limited social connectivity, and decreased job autonomy, satisfaction, and performance (Crippa et al., 2021; Gemine et al., 2021; Oksanen et al., 2021a; Spagnoli et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). In the meanwhile, the experience of emotional and psychological discomfort, coupled with occupational burnout syndrome, has been shown to have detrimental effects on employee morale, dedication to work, psychological well-being, and overall productivity. The issues voiced by remote employees are to their perceived devaluation and lack of confidence in carrying out certain duties.

Keywords: *Burnout, Stress, Employee Burnout and Stress, Performance in Organizational Psychology, Problems in Industrial Psychology*

Introduction

Extended working hours have the potential to expose individuals to burnout and chronic job stress, so adversely affecting not only the quality of their work but also their interpersonal

CURRENT SCIENCE

connections. Consequently, their mental health and psychological well-being may be significantly compromised. The attitudes, views, and experiences associated with remote work have been shown to have a detrimental impact on work-life balance (Crippa et al., 2021; Oksanen et al., 2021b; Van Zoonen et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). As a result, the escalation of symptoms related to emotional tiredness and burnout occurs. The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in rapid organizational adjustments and increased felt stress related to distant labor, exacerbating psychological burnout and strain. Consequently, this resulted in a state of emotional exhaustion. Alongside individual personality characteristics, sociodemographic differences have played a significant role in shaping the culture of distant workplaces. Consequently, these disparities have had a notable impact on psychological distress, heightened risks to mental well-being, and the occurrence of professional burnout. The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in an increase in work-related stress among professionals, which has subsequently contributed to the emergence of technostress and psychological ill-health (Hayes et al., 2021; Miguel-Puga et al., 2021; Trinidad, 2021; Singh et al., 2022), particularly in relation to remote work.

Methodology

The work-life balance was adversely impacted by the presence of chronic burnout, which was brought about by an escalation in job demands. This was shown by the manifestation of many symptoms, including sleep disruption, heightened levels of stress, mood anxiety, and a sense of detachment from reality. The work stress and burnout experienced by workers who are able to perform their job duties remotely because to advancements in technology have been exacerbated as a result of the limitations imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic. Consequently, there was a decline in work productivity. The presence of organizational supports, in conjunction with active involvement in decision-making processes, has been shown to correlate with heightened levels of job satisfaction and improved social-emotional well-being. Additionally, remote employees who experience low levels of stress or inadequate compensation are more likely to exhibit reduced burnout and an increased propensity to leave the organization. The implementation of technology in facilitating remote work has resulted in various negative outcomes such as work fatigue, psychological stress, burnout, and conflicts in achieving work-life balance (Chi et al., 2021;

CURRENT SCIENCE

Oksanen et al., 2021a; Shockley et al., 2021; Vargas Rubilar and Oros, 2021).

This shift has also blurred the distinction between personal and professional domains, consequently diminishing work-related resources. Moreover, individuals with limited technological proficiency and inadequate supervision and guidance have been particularly affected by these challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic. The equilibrium between work and personal life was detrimentally impacted, leading to unfavorable consequences in terms of employment, including employee burnout and attrition, as well as negative effects on emotional and physical well-being and increased workplace stress.

The outcomes of insufficient working circumstances in distant areas, excessive workload, and prolonged efforts to fulfill job requirements were perceived occupational stress, psychophysical symptoms, and job burnout. Research has demonstrated a negative correlation between job burnout and organizational stress with the quality of communication, the establishment of expectations, and the sharing of socially supportive information. Conversely, work-related demands and professional performance exhibit a positive association with job burnout and organizational stress.

Psychological Health

The COVID-19 pandemic has been shown to be linked to work pressures and psychological symptoms, which in turn are connected with occupational burnout, emotional weariness, physical tiredness, and cognitive fatigue (Ingusci et al., 2021; Michel et al., 2021; Ninaus et al., 2021; Salvesen and Berg, 2021). The present circumstances have had an adverse impact on the mental health of the workforce. The implementation of collaborative remote workspaces and the alignment of organizational resources have been shown to enhance work engagement and job performance. Consequently, these improvements have resulted in decreases in cognitive and emotional demands, behavioral stress, time pressure, and occupational demands. The reported levels of physical and cognitive burnout, together with stress-induced mental health issues, had a detrimental effect on job satisfaction and the capacity to maintain a harmonious work-life balance.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Literature Review

Remote employees often expressed concerns over emotional labor, professional burnout, and challenges associated with achieving a satisfactory equilibrium between their work and personal lives (Ayyala et al., 2021; Liberati et al., 2021; Shipman et al., 2021; Upadyaya et al., 2021). Positive work environments, characterized by favorable conditions and supportive contacts, together with regular virtual social interactions among staff members, and the provision of flexible work schedules, coupled with the option to work remotely, have been shown to mitigate burnout and enhance job satisfaction and work-life balance. Consequently, there has been a notable decrease in the levels of stress, worry, and occupational isolation that are associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic has been shown to have a significant impact on employee stress levels and job burnout, resulting in decreased productivity and interruptions in remote work environments. The commitments and limits associated with the job resulted in a decrease in opportunities for social engagement, which subsequently led to heightened feelings of isolation and stress. Employee turnover may occur as a result of several factors, including difficulties in adapting to new circumstances, high levels of stress, and situational demands relating to work practices, social support, and professional assistance. These challenges may be exacerbated by the use of remote access technologies, which can impose additional pressure and time limits on employees.

The enhancement of employee health, productivity, performance, and creativity may be achieved via the implementation of flexible employment practices, efficient time management strategies, and the provision of emotional support within teams. Additionally, the use of this approach has the potential to mitigate stress, anxiety, burnout, and feelings of isolation inside the workplace. Within the framework of the COVID-19 pandemic, enduring psychological stress has been linked to emotional fatigue and diminished professional accomplishments, heightened work demands, and the presence of demanding remote work circumstances that impose emotional and psychological strain (Holmes et al., 2021; Liberati et al., 2021; Van Zoonen et al., 2021).

The provision of assistance by organizations has been essential in mitigating work-related stress, hence contributing to the alleviation of emotions of helplessness. The presence of work-related stressors, such as a heavy workload and job insecurity, has been shown to contribute to an

CURRENT SCIENCE

escalation in work-life conflict. This, in turn, leads to heightened psychological strain and a reduction in perceived social support. Occupational burnout and work-family conflict are influenced by various factors such as stress, tension, and uncertainty in the workplace, as well as the psychological health and fatigue of employees. Additionally, increased cognitive tension and social isolation, along with emotional exhaustion and decreased job satisfaction, have been identified as contributing factors to these phenomena (Allgood et al., 2022; Bakarich et al., 2022; Mosleh et al., 2022; Selvaskandan et al., 2022). Research on the impact of COVID-19 has shown that individuals engaged in remote work have several negative psychological outcomes. These include depersonalization, emotional weariness, role stress and overload, lower personal achievement, and job burnout. These adverse effects significantly contribute to the probability of employees deciding to terminate their employment. The act of burdening staff members with an excessive workload has led to heightened levels of stress, emotional tiredness, professional burnout, and a higher rate of employee turnover.

It is imperative to ascertain the employees' perception of their work as being stressful and attributing it to stressful conditions. This is crucial in order to provide recommendations to management on enhancing employee efficiency, mitigating or eradicating the consequent low performance, and evaluating the adverse impact of job stress and burnout on employee performance. The existing scholarly literature suggests the need for an investigation into the potential adverse impact of stress and burnout on job performance (Grout, 1994:29; Carr). The identification of factors contributing to economic recession inside an organization has significant importance due to its potential impact on the overall economic stability of the nation over an extended period. The results of this study indicate that it would be advisable for the management to consider implementing strategies aimed at educating workers on the topics of stress and burnout, as well as implementing steps to mitigate the potential negative effects associated with these issues. The frequency of this phenomenon has been steadily rising.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Findings

Since the inception of a significant concept in the 1970s, scholars and professionals have been driven to investigate and devise strategies to address, prevent, or counteract it (Schaufeli et al., 2008:204). Numerous writers have made extensive efforts to differentiate between stress and the innate emotional responses that individuals undergo as a biological process, prompted by various stimuli. According to Aswathappa (2009), existing research provides empirical support for the notion that burnout has a detrimental impact on task performance. There is a potential correlation between stress and burnout and the impact it has on employee performance. Consequently, workers within the same work environment may exhibit varying degrees of stress and burnout, contingent upon the strategies used to manage stressors (Aswathappa, 2009:498). According to scholarly sources (Aswathappa, 2009:508, Gill et al., 2006:471, Schaufeli et al., 2008:204), it is posited that the enduring consequences of persistent occupational pressures on the person culminate in a state of burnout. Research has shown that workers who undergo burnout, characterized by physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion, as well as a negative and cynical outlook towards their job, exhibit diminished levels of performance. The organization's overall profitability would be negatively impacted by the suboptimal performance levels shown by its personnel. There are several factors that might lead to a prosperous corporation experiencing prolonged financial losses. It is important to examine if a deteriorating human capital inside the organization, specifically in the context of business process management (BPC), plays a role in this phenomenon. Prior to the commencement of this research, no extant study had been conducted to ascertain the influence of stress and burnout on the overall financial performance of the business.

The concept of "stress" pertains to the detrimental impact of the strain encountered by persons (Aswathappa, 2009:507). According to many writers (Brades & Das, 2006:238; Drafke & Kossen, 2002:409; Aswathappa, 2009:507; Rao, 2005:644), it is widely acknowledged that there are two distinct categories of stress. According to Aswathappa (2009: 507), eustress may be described as a sort of stress that is constructive in nature, serving as a motivating force to enhance an individual's performance. Boredom may be characterized as a kind of stress that is seen as unpleasant. Boredom may be considered a kind of detrimental stress that has negative implications for both individuals and organizations (Drafke and Kossen, 2002:409). Several instances of stress

CURRENT SCIENCE

may be seen, such as the heightened state of anxiety experienced by those who exert significant effort before to examinations, diligently focus during class sessions, and diligently complete projects and assignments within the designated time frame. As to Aswathappa's (2009:497) findings, distress is defined as an excessive level of stress that may lead to the overloading and deterioration of an individual's physical and mental systems. Drafke and Kossen (2002:409) suggest that death ensues from a state referred to as sensory deprivation, which is distinguished by the lack of any kind of stress. Nevertheless, it is important to note that an overwhelming amount of stress has the potential to lead to severe health conditions that may be fatal (Drafke & Kossen, 2002:424; Sargent, 2007:11).

Argument

It is evident that several elements exert effect on the consequences of the stressor-stress relationship. The aforementioned stressors will manifest themselves in diverse ways across different phases of an individual's professional journey. Hence, the aforementioned levels include individual, group, organizational, and non-organizational domains. Numerous writers have identified the contemporary work environment as a significant contributor to stress and burnout. According to Drafke and Kossen (2002:410), Several writers have identified the following factors as the primary sources of stress that eventually result in burnout: quantitative and qualitative demands, control over work speed, attendance, shifts, and job positions. The phenomenon of working extended hours as a result of high labor requirements within a constrained timeframe may be categorized as quantitative demand (Drafke and Kossen, 2002:411; Kaufman, 2005:171; Carr, Kelly, Keaton and Albrecht, 2011:32; Rao, 2005:644). Qualitative demands include several factors that might adversely affect individuals in their professional settings. These factors may include a dearth of decision-making power, a sense of limited autonomy resulting in a perceived loss of control, and the emergence of performance anxiety subsequent to a promotion. Hence, the operational efficiency of the organization may be impeded by substantial bureaucratic delays. Drafke and Kossen (2002:411) claim that work accidents and injuries might manifest due to the adverse behavioral consequences of stress, including indifference and carelessness.

Role Ambiguity

Sources of stress in the workplace include role ambiguity, opposing values, uncertainty, fast change, threats, and dissatisfaction (Smith, 2018). The researchers reached the conclusion that irrespective of the vantage point from which the origins of stress are seen, the impacts of stress on both personnel and the company as a whole may not provide advantageous or desired outcomes. While the veracity of this scenario has yet to be substantiated by empirical investigation, extant literature suggests a correlation between heightened employee stress levels and a concomitant decline in productivity (Rao, 2005:653, Aswathappa, 2009:496). Excessive stress has potential risks in both the short-term and long-term contexts. As stated by Kaufman (2005), the immediate manifestations of stress include weariness, irritability, insomnia, anxiety, and sensations of unease (p. 171). Based on the findings of Sargent (2007) and Grout (1994:29), there exists a potential elevation in the likelihood of developing stomach ulcers, hypertension, migraines, asthma, dermatological conditions, cardiovascular ailments, and stroke when exposed to certain factors for an extended duration. Persistent stress can have detrimental effects on various bodily systems, including the digestive system and glands. These effects may manifest as fatigue, dullness, indigestion, pain, stomach ulcers, coliciritis, constipation, and digestive disturbances that can ultimately result in nutritional deficiencies. Additionally, the neuro-hormonal reproductive system can also be negatively impacted by persistent stress. Furthermore, it is worth noting that several factors such as challenges in menstruation, spermatogenesis, and sexual issues have significant importance (Renaud, 2003: 157). Alder (2005) asserts that work-related stress often serves as a catalyst for the emergence of several ailments, including clinical depression, suicide, deadly cardiovascular conditions, as well as occupational illnesses and injuries. The aforementioned impacts are a matter of worry for employees, since they eventually lead to a decrease in the number of productive hours for employers and result in economic losses for the nation.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Burnout

Several scholars have posited that stress may have both psychological and physiological ramifications on people (Gill et al., 2006:471; Rothmann, Steyn, & Mostert, 2004:55), whilst others argue that stress could elicit a biological or adaptive response (Renaud, 2003:160). The occurrence of burnout may be influenced by prolonged exposure of an individual to stress in the workplace (Rothmann et al., 2004:55; Rao, 2005:660; Whitaker, 1996:61; Buick and Thomas, 2001:304). Throughout history, scholars have endeavored to investigate the many aspects and intricacies associated with the occurrence of work-related stress and burnout. According to Gill et al. (2006:471), burnout may be described as a syndrome or ailment that manifests as physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion, accompanied with a sense of cynicism towards one's career, which arises from prolonged exposure to stress. Individuals who experience depletion are prone to engaging in high-risk activities, such as excessive alcohol use, smoking, and overeating, hence increasing their susceptibility to coronary heart disease. Grout (1994:29) asserts that coronary heart disease is the primary cause of mortality for a significant proportion, namely over 25%, of males between the age range of 35 to 44. Maslach et al. (1993, 1996, 2001) have posited that burnout is a psychological phenomenon characterized by emotional tiredness, depersonalization, and diminished personal performance.

Burnout is characterized by significant distress and a profound sense of emptiness experienced by individuals. Consequently, a considerable number of individuals affected by burnout resort to engaging in behaviors such as alcohol consumption, drug use, gambling, and sexual activities as a means of seeking comfort (Benson, 2005:176). According to the findings of Schaufeli and Enzmann (1998), as cited by Rothman et al. (2004:55), burnout may be defined as an enduring unpleasant emotional state that arises in the context of work, and is marked by a range of physical, psychological, and behavioral manifestations. Fatigue is considered to be the most significant factor among them. The Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) was established by a group of researchers and subsequently used by scholars and professionals in many fields as a tool for assessing the level of burnout experienced by individuals in the workforce.

According to reports, the use of MBI had a significant surge in popularity towards the conclusion of the 1990s, leading to its selection as the preferred technique of analysis in around

CURRENT SCIENCE

93% of academic publications and theses. There is a growing acknowledgement among researchers and practitioners that burnout is not limited to the human services sector, but also affects managers themselves (Buick and Thomas 2001:305) (Maslach & Leiter, 2008). While burnout was first conceptualized primarily in the context of humanitarian services, scholars and professionals have increasingly acknowledged the occurrence of burnout in domains outside human services (Maslach & Leiter, 2008). The aforementioned statement holds true due to the fact that burnout has emerged as a significant worldwide issue (Maslach et al., 2009). Freudenberger (1974) introduced the term "burnout" to characterize the state of exhaustion resulting from prolonged stress, as seen via personal encounters with burnout on two distinct occasions. The aforementioned study conducted by Schaufeli et al. (2009:205) contributed to the enhancement of Freudenberger's credibility in public speaking about the issue at hand. Since its inception, the area of burnout has seen significant expansion, leading to the emergence of experts worldwide that specialize in providing treatment for those suffering from burnout. Moreover, burnout is officially acknowledged as a medical condition in Europe, enabling afflicted employees to pursue compensation claims and avail themselves of treatment programs (Schaufelietal., 2009:205).

Performance

Prior to commencing the measurement or administration of performance, it is essential to possess a comprehensive comprehension of the notion of "performance." It is important to ascertain the specific aspects of staff monitoring that will enable us to identify the potential impact of stress on their performance. Only by doing a thorough analysis can we ascertain if stress plays a significant role. The concept of performance has been the subject of much investigation and may be characterized from several perspectives. The objective is not to delve extensively into the intricacies and determinants that impact performance; instead, it is crucial for our objectives to acquire a fundamental comprehension of the subject matter.

It is well acknowledged that an artist may exhibit both exceptional and unfavorable qualities. This assertion has validity at both the individual and institutional levels. Armstrong and

CURRENT SCIENCE

Baron (2006) argue that performance may be comprehended as a representation of an individual's accomplishments at the individual level (p. 15). From an organizational standpoint, performance encompasses a wide range of factors, including the behaviors shown by workers, the outcomes they achieve, and the effectiveness of the systems and procedures used to carry out tasks (Armstrong and Baron, 2006:16). According to the Oxford Compact Thesaurus, performance may be described as the sustained execution, fulfillment, accomplishment, completion, leadership, and overall execution of a single task (Oxford Compact Thesaurus). The organizational profitability is influenced either favorably or adversely by the level of efficiency with which work is executed. The executive team is responsible for formulating a set of strategic decisions aimed at attaining a defined objective and establishing a competitive edge for the firm vis-à-vis other enterprises. The most basic manifestation of these judgments is the execution of a singular job. Hence, it is important to ascertain the potential influence of stress and burnout on the execution of the specific activity inside the BPC.

Stress and Burnout

The distinction between work stress and burnout may be subject to variation based on an individual's perception and reaction to stressors. It is important to acknowledge that the cognitive processes play a crucial role in this differentiation (Renaud, 2003:161). While acknowledging the multifaceted impact of employee stress, it is essential to effectively address and mitigate this issue in order to prevent its progression into a chronic state. If the state of unmanaged stress persists, it may ultimately escalate to a critical level that poses a potential fatality risk for individuals, perhaps resulting in irreversible harm and mortality (Alder, 2005:146). Conversely, it has been proposed that the exhaustion stage is the ultimate phase characterized by the absence of heat or flame, leaving only coal and debris visible (Schaufeli et al., 2009:214).

1. *The person feels tired*
2. *Experiences chronic fatigue*
3. *The person is worried*
4. *The individual is hypertensive*

CURRENT SCIENCE

5. *Person is dissatisfied with his job*
6. *The individual is bored with his job and is cynical*
7. *Decreased work engagement*
8. *The individual's commitment to work is almost nil*
9. *Mentally disconnected from the organization*
10. *The person feels pessimistic*
11. *The individual feels impatient, irritable and does not want to talk to others.*
12. *The person feels guilty*
13. *The individual experiences a mental breakdown*
14. *The person has difficulty concentrating; tends to forget things*
15. *The individual does not seem to know where he is; forgetfulness becomes more frequent*
16. *Physiological changes occur in the person, such as increased blood pressure and heart rate.*
17. *The individual begins to express his psychosomatic complaints.*¹

Managing Stress and Burnout

Stress reduction solutions may be classified into two main categories: individual strategies and organizational strategies. According to the writers, the following statements were made: Numerous coping mechanisms may be used by people to mitigate the adverse effects of stress on their well-being. According to Aswathappa (2009:496), The aforementioned strategies include muscular relaxation, biofeedback, meditation, cognitive restructuring, and good time management approaches. Furthermore, Aswathappa (2009:505) asserts that there is no universally applicable methodology for effectively managing and mitigating stress levels. According to Jeff Grout (1994:30), people are advised to adopt a healthy lifestyle as a means of successful stress management. This includes the consumption of a balanced food, the reduction of smoking and alcohol use, and the frequent engagement in physical exercise to maintain an acceptable body

¹ Source: Adapted from Aswathappa (2006:502)

CURRENT SCIENCE

weight. The author posits that implementing a comprehensive set of lifestyle modifications including dietary adjustments, physical activity, and relaxation techniques may enable people to effectively cope with stress in their daily lives.

Organizational Strategies

Organizational strategies that can be used for stress relief often include:

- (a) *the physical working environment,*
- (b) *Redesigning the job to eliminate stressors,*
- (c) *Changes in workload, deadlines and structural reorganization etc. (Aswathappa, 2009:505).*

Two key elements of stress management programs are team building and behavior adjustment. These components are designed to modify individuals' perspectives and perceptions of stress, as well as their understanding of its impact, by addressing both present and past experiences.

Workshops focusing on subjects such as time management and burnout might be quite beneficial in reducing the likelihood of encountering these adverse consequences. As stated by Aswathappa (2006:506), it is possible to provide staff with training in relaxing techniques and include them into physical fitness initiatives. According to Drafke and Kossen (2002:425), Numerous researchers have identified a wide range of relaxation treatments available to people for the purpose of promoting relaxation and alleviating stress (Author, 200x 149; JeffGrout, 1994:29; Carr et al. 2011:32; Drafke&Kossen, 2002:409). Nevertheless, finding a certain time and location in which the probability of encountering any kind of stress is very low continues to be a formidable challenge. Indeed, it seems that stress cannot be entirely eradicated as long as we persist within a life cycle that necessitates the pursuit of a satisfactory standard of living and the responsibility of nurturing one's progeny and contributing to society as a whole. The literature extensively

CURRENT SCIENCE

documents the well-established detrimental physical and psychological effects associated with stress and burnout. The recently found remedies have the objective of enhancing the manageability of stress and burnout symptoms, while also reducing their potentially fatal consequences. Research has shown a correlation between stress and burnout in the workplace and negative outcomes such as decreased staff performance and increased rates of absenteeism. These consequences have a harmful effect on the overall organizational performance (Aswathappa, 2009:507; Maslach et al., 2009).

Duraisingam et al. assert that an abundance of stress within the professional environment has an adverse influence on workers, so diminishing their dedication to their occupational roles and subsequently influencing their inclination to seek other employment opportunities. Individuals may experience heightened levels of frustration and fatigue when faced with excessive workloads, frequent changes in their environment, a dearth of performance evaluations, and diminishing remuneration. This phenomenon has a detrimental influence on individuals' conduct, eventually culminating in their decision to resign from their employment. Several factors, including prolonged operational hours, diverse behaviors, a company strategy defined by limited resources and high demand, and little feedback, might contribute to a significant level of burnout and stress. Workplace burnout and stress are two significant elements that, over an extended period, result in a decline in work performance and an elevated probability of employee attrition. In recent years, there has been a growing scholarly interest in the work demands experienced by employees. However, it is worth noting that the bulk of research endeavors have mostly concentrated on fields such as accounting, sales, and nursing, with relatively little attention given to the job demands of staff.

When an individual surpasses a certain threshold of stress, both the physiological and psychological aspects of the body and mind initiate a response that may be likened to preparing for combat, as shown by observable behavioral and psychological responses. The significance of job burnout as a pressing concern requires substantial consideration from scholars and corporate executives alike. Previous research has shown a correlation between diminished levels of organizational commitment and various adverse responses towards one's career or work, such as experiencing discontentment with their existing position and displaying an atypical inclination

CURRENT SCIENCE

towards changing their vocation or job. The results of many research indicate that there is a significant correlation between employee burnout and substantial financial implications for both workers and businesses. The aforementioned expenses are evident via a significant decrease in productivity, a rise in absence rates, and an increase in staff turnover. The occurrence of burnout within an individual's present role is a significant determinant for forecasting both work happiness and the likelihood of future intents to depart from such employment. The prevailing body of research primarily investigates the impact of work-related stress on an individual's inclination to resign from their employment. Additionally, other studies have been undertaken to examine the phenomenon of work burnout and its impact on employees' decisions to discontinue their employment with a particular organization. Nevertheless, a dearth of existing literature exists in relation to the investigation of the correlation between employee turnover and workplace stress, as well as the role that job burnout assumes in connecting these two phenomena. In addition to discerning the adverse consequences of work-related stress on the occurrence of job burnout, it is essential to explore the influence of job burnout and job stress on employees' inclination to depart from their present employment positions.

Stress at Work

There is a widely held belief among individuals that job stress is a significant occupational hazard with profound implications for the well-being of workers across many global contexts. The word "stress" refers to the application of physical or psychological strain on an individual by those in positions of authority or other duly authorized individuals. work stress may be understood in several ways, such as a negative emotional state, a burden, a reaction to work stressors, a psychological condition, and a distinctive addiction. Occupational stress refers to the incapacity or pressure experienced in the workplace when individuals have difficulties in effectively fulfilling job tasks due to a misalignment between their skills and the demands and circumstances of the job. The elements that influence an individual's degree of work-related stress may be categorized into two distinct groups: internal and external. The cognitive processes, strategies, and other dimensions of these occurrences may be attributed to endogenous factors. These factors are attributed to the person and serve as a significant contributor to psychological distress. The

CURRENT SCIENCE

interpretation of these perspectives is contingent upon the subjective viewpoint of each individual. Despite the absence of immediate physical danger, individuals may experience fatigue when exposed to an unfavorable environment or when faced with an intimidating individual. The phrase "external causes" encompasses a diverse range of external elements that exist inside a business and detrimentally affect an individual's performance within that enterprise. Elements such as control in the workplace, working hours, employment instability, management style, overload, and underload are included under this area. Employees may experience stress when they are faced with situations that need changes in their conduct. The psychological risks associated with working stress may be classified into three distinct categories:

- (a) *Job uncertainty,*
- (b) *Increasing workload and*
- (c) *An imbalance between one's personal life and professional responsibilities.*

The non-compliance of corporations with their contractual duties has led to the deprivation of job prospects, so inducing a state of ambiguity and distress among the labor force. Individuals are required to manage augmented workloads and elevated levels of labor on a daily basis. The issues that people encounter at home may be attributed to several factors, including work-related stress, heightened workload, and the prevailing uncertainty around job prospects.

The experience of anxiety resulting from job is associated with worse outcomes. The presence of work-related stress has been shown to be associated with several behavioral issues, such as engaging in unfavorable interactions with coworkers, experiencing higher rates of absenteeism, and a progressive deterioration in overall morale. This particular kind of stress may also lead to a continuous decline in morale. Occupational stress is influenced by two key structural components, namely role ambiguity and role conflict. Role conflict occurs when an individual is confronted with many demands pertaining to their job and is unable to fulfill these expectations concurrently. The concept of "role ambiguity," conversely, pertains to situations in which individuals have uncertainty about their job responsibilities or lack a satisfactory degree of proficiency in their jobs, resulting in an inability to fulfill workplace expectations effectively.

CURRENT SCIENCE

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the phenomenon of burnout, driven by a desire to better understand its profound negative effects on individuals within the professional setting. Consequently, there has been a surge in the quantity of research conducted on the topic. Workplace burnout is a significant threat to the psychosomatic well-being of persons encountered in the professional setting. The confluence of both internal and external factors has a deleterious impact on an individual's psychosomatic well-being, hence serving as a significant stressor. Psychosocial factors that contribute to workplace stress include extended working hours, job instability, greater workload, potential negative outcomes for compensation and advancement, ambiguous project responsibilities, and time and budget demands that may lead to mistakes and compromised ethical and quality standards. Additional elements that lead to burnout include unfavorable circumstances pertaining to compensation and advancement. There exists a correlation between burnout and employee turnover. Burnout is a stress reaction often seen in those that engage in direct and intensive interpersonal interactions, such as students, clients, or visitors. The significance of time loss due to an overwhelming quantity of tasks, meetings, and other obligations should not be overlooked.

Breaking Point

Although stress may have some positive effects in some situations, it is important to acknowledge that individuals have their own limits and thresholds when it comes to coping with stress. When beyond certain thresholds, the probability of encountering burnout is heightened. The phenomenon of burnout within the workplace has been shown to have a detrimental impact on production levels, resulting in a decline, as well as an increase in the rate of employee turnover. Burnout has a deleterious influence on the human physiological and psychological systems, thus leading to adverse effects on performance and production. Burnout is a distinct kind of emotional fatigue that manifests in young volunteers who exhibit elevated degrees of dedication towards their job setting. This kind of emotional weariness is correlated with insufficient effort, commitment, and diminished motivation. Maslach characterizes this scenario as a state of apathy and disinterest towards the clientele of the organization. Indeed, office burnout is a psychosomatic phenomenon that is intricately linked to the stress individuals encounter within their professional environment.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Indeed, job burnout is a kind of psychological fatigue accompanied by mental strain that is associated with the nature of one's employment and the conditions inside the office setting. This answer is a belated acknowledgment of the factors that contribute to persistent interpersonal stress and occupational mobility. These factors are likely to manifest in professions that include the management and guidance of individuals, as well as the fulfillment of accompanying responsibilities and obligations. Work burnout is a prominent and readily observable sign of occupational stress.

Effects of Overwork

The phenomenon known as job burnout syndrome has been shown to have detrimental effects on the physical and psychological well-being of workers. These effects include decreased job satisfaction, diminished quality of work output, and many work-related issues such as continually shifting expectations and high job pressure without adequate support systems. Various variables might potentially contribute to the development of work burnout syndrome. A positive association has been observed between several personality qualities and a heightened susceptibility to experiencing job burnout. These traits include work orientation, desire for assertiveness, and idealism. According to Maslach (year), job burnout may be seen as a psychological reaction to the personal and emotional stresses that individuals experience within their profession or workplace. This response manifests in unpleasant emotions, including feelings of reduced accomplishment, decreased productivity, and inefficiency in the work environment. Several key variables contribute to the occurrence of professional burnout. One significant element is emotional weariness, which encompasses a spectrum of experiences ranging from mild boredom to severe despair. This may manifest in behaviors such as treating people in a dispassionate way and experiencing a lack of personal fulfillment.

The concept of "job burnout" is a state that may arise due to extended and recurrent encounters with demanding circumstances within the professional environment, resulting in diverse degrees of exhaustion including physical, mental, and emotional aspects. Workplace burnout is a prevalent issue among workers across many organizations, exerting adverse impacts

CURRENT SCIENCE

on both individuals and the overall efficacy of institutions, thereby leading to detrimental consequences for employees. Job burnout may be attributed to several risk factors, including inadequate workplace support, diminished motivation, insufficient clarification, ineptitude, heightened workload, and unreasonable performance expectations. Additionally, it encompasses indicators that suggest a prevalence of interpersonal relationships and feelings of withdrawal, along with challenges pertaining to familial dynamics, physical well-being, and academic/professional achievement. Hence, it is important for managers to implement suitable strategies aimed at fostering a conducive work environment, hence reducing the risk of workers experiencing burnout-related difficulties.

Conclusion

The phenomenon of workplace burnout has been shown to be associated with a heightened reliance on alcohol use, which often displays as aggressive and antagonistic behavior within the work environment. When workers experience job satisfaction and see themselves to be achieving or surpassing their full potential, it is logical to expect that they could willingly provide assistance to others in tasks that are linked to their work. The state of exhaustion may give rise to fluctuations in mood, which in turn may result in the abuse of others. Likewise, those who see themselves as having lower levels of competence and proficiency in their endeavors tend to have the belief that they lack the ability to effectively manage their anger. Regrettably, little consideration has been given to the correlation between mistreatment by colleagues and occupational burnout, as well as the occurrence of sabotage resulting from adverse work environments. According to the theoretical framework, burnout is characterized by three fundamental components: depersonalization, diminished personal achievements, and emotional exhaustion. These characteristics exhibit interconnections. Burnout is a phenomenon seen among employees when they get disengaged from their work and exhibit less care for their clients, leading to a heightened level of negative emotions and resentment, which might vary based on their specific employment circumstances. The phenomenon is associated with the depletion of resources and the erosion of individual characteristics. This study forecasts a significant prevalence of adverse employee-related outcomes, including absenteeism and turnover. Moreover, there exists a correlation between this

CURRENT SCIENCE

phenomenon and adverse psychological consequences, including but not limited to depressive symptoms, disruptions in sleep patterns, and engagement in substance abuse, including alcohol and drug use. The concept of "employee turnover" pertains to the phenomenon whereby workers choose to voluntarily terminate their employment inside an organization. The departure of an employee from a firm may have significant negative consequences, both for the individual and for the organization as a whole. The concept of "turnover intention" refers to the probability of a person voluntarily terminating their present employment within a relatively little timeframe. Put otherwise, the objective of the employee is to seek employment in a different organization. The desire to switch occupations may also be construed as the objective to conclude one's employment in a certain setting. A high rate of employee turnover is often seen as unfavorable and is regarded as an expensive issue due to its detrimental impact on quality. Another drawback is to the continuous need of recruiting fresh personnel and equipping them with suitable training. Within the realm of healthcare, there is an expectation that it will have adverse consequences in terms of delivering a satisfactory level of service that aligns with the demands of customers.

RESTRICTION

In this study, which is built around a better understanding of the relationship between the phenomena of power and social control, the boundaries of these two concepts are determined and this evaluation is carried out with the information provided from the sources obtained by taking into account the scope of the research. This study is globally limited to the scientific studies on the subject.

NOTICES

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external experts.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Financial Support: The author did not report any financial support for the study.

ETHICS DECLARATION

The publication ethics of this journal; It is a scientific journal in the field of social sciences that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with the main criteria specified as openness, honesty, respect for the findings and work of other publishers and objectivity.

References

- Ali M., Bilal H., Raza B., Ghani MU Examining the Influence of Workplace Bullying on Job Burnout: Mediating Effect of Psychological Capital and Psychological Contract Violation. *int. J. Organ. leadersh.* 2019; 8:1–11. doi: 10.33844/ijol.2019.60467.
- Ali N., Ali A. The Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction between Psychological Capital and Job Burnout of Pakistani Nurses. *J. Commer. Soc. sci.* 2014; 8:399–412.
- Bianchi R., Truchot D., Laurent E., Brisson R., Schonfeld IS leader's burnout solely job-related? A critical comment. *scand. J. Psychol.* 2014; 55:357–361. doi: 10.1111/sjop.12119. [PubMed]
- Chiang, C.-F.; Liu, B.-Z. Examining job stress and burnout of hotel room attendants: Internal marketing and organizational commitment as moderators. *J. Hum. Resour. Hosp. tour.* 2017, 16, 1–17.
- Chromy, J.R. Snowball Sampling. In *Encyclopedia of Survey Research Methods*; Lavrakas, P., Ed.; Sage Publications, Inc.: Thousand Oaks, CA, USA, 2008.

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Dionisi, T., Sestito, L., Tarli, C., Antonelli, M., Tosoni, A., D'Addio, S., et al. (2021). Risk of burnout and stress in physicians working in a COVID team: a longitudinal survey. *int. J. Clin. practice* 75, e14755. doi: 10.1111/ijcp.14755
- Dobson-Lohman, E., and Potcovaru, A.-M. (2020). Fake news content shaping the COVID-19 pandemic fear: virus anxiety, emotional contagion, and responsible media reporting. *Anal. metaphys* 19. 94–100. doi: 10.22381/AM19202011
- Gemine, R., Davies, GR, Tarrant, S., Davies, RM, James, M., and Lewis, K. (2021). Factors associated with work-related burnout in NHS staff during COVID-19: a cross-sectional mixed methods study. *BMJOpen*. 11, e042591. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2020-042591
- Gil-Monte PR, Olivares-Faúndez VE, Jélvez-Wilke C., Mena L., Figueiredo-Ferraz H. Relationships between burnout and role ambiguity, role conflict and employee absenteeism among health workers. *Sweat. Psychol.* 2014; 32:111–120.
- Hair, JF; Black, WC; Babin, BJ; Anderson, RE *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 7th ed.; Prentice Hall: Hoboken, NJ, USA, 2010.
- Jung, HS; Yoon, HH; Kim, YJ Effects of culinary employees' role stress on burnout and turnover intention in hotel industry: Moderating effects on employees' tenure. *serv. Ind. J.* 2012, 32, 2145–2165.
- Khafi A., Ghasemi M. The Relation between Job Burnout and Work and Family Conflict among Employees. *J. Res. Giant.* 2014; 2:26–30.
- Khalatbari J., Ghorbanshiroudi S., Firouzbakhsh M. Correlation of Job Stress, Job Satisfaction, Job Motivation and Burnout and Feeling Stress. *procedural -Soc. Behav. sci.* 2013; 84:860–863. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.06.662.
- Li X., Jiang T., Sun J., Shi L., Liu J. The relationship between occupational stress, job burnout and quality of life among surgical nurses in Xinjiang, China. *BMC Nurs.* 2021; 20:1–11. doi: 10.1186/s12912-021-00703-2.

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Liu, N., Xu, Z., and Skare, M. (2021). The research on COVID-19 and economy from 2019 to 2020: analysis from the perspective of bibliometrics. *oecon. Copernic* 12, 217–268. doi: 10.24136/oc.2021.09
- Lyons, N., and Lăzăroi, G. (2020). Addressing the COVID-19 crisis by harnessing Internet of Things sensors and machine learning algorithms in data-driven smart sustainable cities. *Geopolite. Hush. int. Relat.* 12, 65–71. doi: 10.22381/GHIR12220209
- Mahmoud, AB, Hack-Polay, D., Reisel, WD, Fuxman, L., Grigoriou, N., Mohr, I., et al. (2021). Who's more vulnerable? a generational investigation of COVID-19 perceptions' effect on organizational citizenship behaviors in the MENA region: job insecurity, burnout and job satisfaction as mediators. *BMC Public Health.* 21, 1951. doi: 10.1186/s12889-021-11976-2
- Makhdoom IF, Atta M., Malik NI Counterproductive Work Behaviors as an Outcome of Job Burnout among High School Teachers. *bull. Educ. pic.* 2019; 41:79–92.
- Mardani S., Mardani N. The Impact of Psychological Empowerment on Job Burnout in Hospital Staff. *int. J.Hosp. pic.* 2014; 3:69–78.
- Mihalca, L., Ratiu, L., Bredeea, G., Metz, D., Dragan, M., and Dobre, F. (2021). Exhaustion while teleworking during COVID-19: a moderated-mediation model of role clarity, self-efficacy, and task interdependence. *oecon. Copernic* 12, 269–306. doi: 10.24136/oc.2021.010
- Mojasa-Kajaob J., Golonka K., Marek T. Burnout and Engagement Among Teachers—Worklife Areas and Personality Traits as Predictors of Relationships with Work. *int. J. Occup. Med. Environ. health.* 2015; 28:102–119. doi: 10.13075/ijomeh.1896.00238.
- Nabi Khan S. The Relationship between Job Burnout and Gender-Based Socio-Demographic Characteristics in Lahore. *Lahore J. Bus.* 2013; 1:65–95. doi: 10.35536/ljb. 2013.v1.i2.a4.
- Podsakoff, PM; MacKenzie, SB; Lee, JY; Podsakoff, NP Common method biases in behavioral research: A critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *J.Appl. Psychol.* 2003, 88, 879–903.

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Prasetio P., Partono A., Wulansari P., Putri ST, Ramdhani R., Abdullah A. The Mediation of Job Satisfaction in the Relation of Work Stress and Turnover Intention in Hotel Industry. *Adv. econ. bus. Manag. pic.* 2018; 65:608–612. doi: 10.2991/icebef-18.2019.130.
- Preacher KJ, Rucker DD, Hayes AF Addressing Moderated Mediation Hypotheses: Theory, Methods, and Prescriptions. *Multivar. Behav. pic.* 2007; 42:185–227. doi: 10.1080/00273170701341316. [PubMed]
- Qattan, AMN The Effect of Work-Related Stress and Burnout on Nursing Performance and Job Satisfaction: A Study of Hospitals in Saudi Arabia. Ph.D. Thesis, Shiefeled University, Sheffield, England, 2017.
- Rizzo, JR; House, RJ; Lirtzman, SI Role Conflict and Ambiguity in Complex Organizations. *Step. sci. Q.* 1970, 15, 150.
- Rodríguez-Ardura, I.; Meseguer-Artola, A. Editorial: How to Prevent, Detect and Control Common Method Variance in Electronic Commerce Research. *J. Theor. Appl. Electron. Comm. pic.* 2020, 15, 1–5.
- Roy S., Novak T., Miksaj-Todorovic L. Job Burnout among Prison Staff in the United States and Croatia: A Preliminary Comparative Study. *int. J. Crim. Justice Sci.* 2010; 5:189–202.
- Santhanam N., Srinivas S. Modeling the impact of employee engagement and happiness on burnout and turnover intention among blue-collar workers at a manufacturing company. *Benchmarking Int. J.* 2019; 27:499–516. doi: 10.1108/BIJ-01-2019-0007.
- Shrefler, KM; Meadows, MP; Davis, KD Firefighting and Fathering: Work-Family Conflict, Parenting Stress, and Satisfaction with Parenting and Child Behavior. *father. A J. Theory Res. Pr. Men's Father.* 2011, 9, 169–188.
- Soelton M., Lestari PA, Arief H., Putra RL the Effect of Role Conflict and Burnout Toward Turnover Intention at Software Industries, Work Stress as Moderating Variables. *Adv. Econ. Bus. Manag. pic.* 2019; 120:185–190. doi: 10.2991/aebmr.k.200205.034.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Wibowo A., Setiawan M., Yuniarinto A. The Effect of Workloads on Turnover Intention with Work Stress as Mediation and Social Support as Moderated Variables. *J. Appl. Manage.* 2021; 19:404–412. doi: 10.21776/ub.jam.2021.019.02.16.

Yousefy A., Ghassemi GR Job burnout in psychiatric and medical nurses in Isfahan, Islamic Republic of Iran. *east. mediterr. Health J.* 2006; 12:662–669.